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Mechanoresponsive Luminescent Polymer Blends Based on an Excimer-Forming Telechelic Macromolecule^a

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A well-known approach towards mechanochromic polymers relies on the incorporation of excimer-forming fluorophores into a matrix polymer and the disruption of aggregated chromophores when such materials undergo macroscopic mechanical deformation. However, the required aggregates and stress-transfer processes have so far only been realized with select dye/polymer combinations. As demonstrated here, the utility of this approach can be extended by tethering an excimer-forming cyano-substituted oligo(*p*-phenylene vinylene) fluorophore to the two ends of a telechelic poly(ethylene-*co*-butylene) and blending small amounts (0.1–

^a **Supporting Information** is available online from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

2 wt%) of the resulting aggregachromic macromolecule into polymer matrices such as poly(ϵ -caprolactone), poly(isoprene), or poly(styrene-*b*-butadiene-*b*-styrene). All blends display mechanofluorochromic responses, and the ratio between the monomer and excimer emission intensities can be used to correlate the luminescence signal to the extent of deformation and to follow subsequent relaxation processes. The developed approach, hence, significantly expands the scope of blend-based mechanoresponsive luminescent materials.

FIGURE FOR ToC_ABSTRACT

1. Introduction

Polymers that respond to (excessive) deformation by changing their optical appearance, such as their reflectance, absorbance, or fluorescence are useful to investigate failure modes and degradation processes,^[1-5] as tamper-proof packaging materials, stress-sensors for structural health monitoring, and other applications.^[6] Typical strategies to translate mechanical stimulation into an optical signal include the deformation of photonic structures,^[7] the damage-induced release of reagents or dyes from capsules,^[8-10] the use of mechanophores that undergo optical changes upon bond cleavage,^{[5],[11-14]} and the spatial separation of mechanically interlocked fluorophore and quencher moieties.^[15]

A simple, scalable, but so far not easily generalizable approach involves blending polymers with dyes whose intermolecular interactions are changed through mechanical stimulation.^[16] For example, mechanical stress was shown to modulate the fluorescence resonance energy transfer (FRET) between rhodamine donor and azulene acceptor dyes in polyethylene,^[17] or between 4-methylcoumarin as a donor and poly(ether urea-*b*-tetrahydrofuran) with a naphthalimide acceptor in the soft blocks.^[18] Prior to these studies, Weder and co-workers, introduced aggregachromic (fluorescent) dyes as probes of mechanical deformation in polymers.^[19] The strategy takes advantage of the large shift of fluorescence emission when intermolecular aggregates of excimer-forming dyes such as cyano-substituted oligo(*p*-phenylene vinylene) (cyano-OPV) derivatives are separated into monomers.^[20] Aggregation-dependent changes of the absorption characteristics can be exploited in a similar manner.^[21] The formation of dye aggregates of adequate size and an efficient stress-transfer from the polymer were identified as key requirements, as first demonstrated when low concentrations (0.1–0.5 wt%) of a cyano-OPV were blended with linear low-density poly(ethylene) (LLDPE).^{[19],[22]} Plastic polymer deformation was shown to disrupt the dye aggregates that had formed in the amorphous portion of the matrix, causing a visually detectable fluorescence

color change from excimer- to monomer-dominated emission. Mechanochromic LLDPE/cyano-OPV blends can be readily obtained by melt-mixing, and aggregates are furnished through local phase separation upon cooling. Great care must be taken to prevent large-scale aggregate formation,^[22] which can be ensured by adjusting the molecular structure, concentration, and processing conditions.^[16] The outlined approach has provided mechanochromic fluorescent materials with cyano-OPVs in poly(ethylene),^[23] polyester,^[24] polyamide,^[25] and poly(vinylidene fluoride) matrices.^[26] In addition, perylene derivatives and 4,4-bis(2-benzoxazolyl)stilbene have been employed in LLDPE,^[27,28] and stilbene derivatives in thermoplastics such as poly(1,4-butylene succinate)^[29] or poly(propylene).^[30] The matrices employed in these studies are all semicrystalline and exhibit plastic deformation behavior, features that appear beneficial to obtain sufficiently small dye aggregates and ensure efficient stress-transfer. By contrast, blends of aggregachromic dyes with poly(urethane) elastomers display only minor changes of the emission spectra upon deformation,^[31] and covalent incorporation of a cyano-OPV derivative into the polymer backbone was necessary to obtain a poly(urethane) with a similar mechanochromic response.^[32]

We show here that the scope of mechanochromic blends can be greatly extended by tethering the chromophore to the two ends of a telechelic polymer and blending the resulting aggregachromic macromolecule into a matrix of interest. Based on the speculation that a dye-functionalized macromolecule entangles either with itself or with the matrix polymer, a reduction of dye mobility during processing is expected, so that small aggregates are formed by a nucleation-dominated, transport-limited process. In addition, the stress transfer to the chromophores should be improved if entanglements are retained after formation of the aggregates. We demonstrate here that a telechelic poly(ethylene-*co*-butylene) with cyano-OPV moieties at the termini meets these expectations and imparts mechanochromic behavior to very different polymers.

2. Results and Discussion

To prepare the targeted chromophore-functionalized macromolecule, an asymmetric cyano-OPV derivative with only one functional terminus was required. The desired cyano-OPV **1** was directly accessed via Knoevenagel condensation between 2,5-dimethoxyterephthalaldehyde and two different nitrile derivatives (**Figures 1a,S1**). The fluorescence spectrum of a dilute chloroform solution of **1** ($c = 0.09 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$) features a maximum at 505 nm, whereas the dried microcrystalline solid **1** displays a maximum at 617 nm (**Figure S2**), which is characteristic of excimer emission for cyano-OPVs.^{[19–21],[23–26]} With the aggregachromic behavior of **1** established, its esterification reaction with bis-acyl chloride terminated telechelic poly(ethylene-*co*-butylene) (PEB) was carried out to prepare the dye-functionalized macromolecule **2** (**Figure 1a,S3**).^[33] The quantitative functionalization of **2** with cyano-OPV **1** was confirmed by NMR and mass spectrometry (see Supporting Information for details). While the fluorescence spectra of chloroform solutions of **2** ($c = 1.4 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$) exclusively show monomer-based emission with a maximum at 505 nm (**Figure S4**), drying of the latter provided a self-supporting film of polymeric appearance that displayed the characteristic orange, excimer-dominated emission of aggregated cyano-OPVs under illumination with UV light ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 365 \text{ nm}$), with an emission maximum at 636 nm (**Figure 1b**).

The differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) traces of a solvent-cast film of **2** show the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the soft PEB backbone at ca. $-49 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and two additional endothermic transitions at around 102 and 116 $^\circ\text{C}$, which appear to be associated with the melting of crystalline chromophore domains (**Figure S5**). This interpretation is supported by the cooling traces, which show exothermic transitions around 120 and 89 $^\circ\text{C}$ that persist if the sample is heated and cooled a second time, indicative of crystallization events. The second heating scan shows a slight shift of the upper melting transition to higher temperatures (126 $^\circ\text{C}$), but no further changes are observed in additional heating or cooling scans. A comparison of the fluorescence spectra of films of **2** recorded at room temperature and upon

heating to 116 and 126 °C shows that the excimer-based emission at 636 nm gives way to the characteristic, monomer-based emission centered around 525 nm (**Figure 1b,S6**), indicating full dissociation of the excimer aggregates above the melting transition. Upon cooling, the excimer-based emission was recovered, although a small amount of green monomer emission persists (**Figure S6**). Thus, in combination, these findings suggest (i) phase separation between the cyano-OPV termini and the PEB backbone; (ii) (partial) crystallization of the cyano-OPV domains; (iii) a processing-dependent polymorphism in the latter, which has previously been observed for related low-molecular weight cyano-OPV derivatives,^[34,35] and was shown to impart such molecules with mechanoresponsive luminescence behavior.^[36]

The response of **2** to a mechanical stimulus was subsequently investigated by grinding the solid polymer film. Even after extensive deformation, however, no visually detectable fluorescence color change was observed, and measurements of the emission revealed no changes either (**Figure 2c**). Speculating that the high concentration of cyano-OPV moieties in the neat **2** might prevent efficient separation of aggregates by mechanical force and/or promote energy transfer from individual cyano-OPVs to remaining aggregates, we diluted **2** with the parent PEB ($M_n = 3100 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$). As clearly discernible in photographs recorded under UV light illumination ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 365 \text{ nm}$), the viscous fluid obtained by mixing PEB and **2** (90:10 w/w) indeed displays an immediate change from an excimer-rich orange to monomer-dominated green emission upon shearing (**Figure 1d and Supporting Movie M1**). When the mechanical stimulation was halted, the monomer-based emission color disappeared within a few seconds, indicating that the system is highly dynamic. While the rapid relaxation prevented spectroscopic analysis, the experiments clearly confirm that a transient disassembly of the cyano-OPV aggregates into the monomeric species occurs upon mechanical stimulation. The stress-transfer between PEB as the majority component of the mixture and **2** must occur via chain entanglements, and although their number is estimated to be as low as 1–

2 per chain, based on the entanglement molecular weight of related PEBs,^[37,38] macroscopically applied shearing stresses are apparently transferred to individual dye aggregates.

The reversible mechanochromic response of a mixture of PEB and **2** indicates that the latter could potentially impart mechanochromism to a wide range of polymers. To test this hypothesis, we prepared blends of **2** with several polymers that, to the best of our knowledge, have so far not been rendered mechanochromic by simple dispersion of an aggregachromic dye, including poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL), poly(isoprene) (PI), and poly(styrene-*b*-butadiene-*b*-styrene) (SBS).^[5] Our efforts were focused on the thermoplastic elastomer SBS, since previous studies with polyurethane elastomers suggested that deformation would not cause the disruption of small-molecule dye aggregates in this matrix (*vide supra*). Thus, blends of SBS (30 wt% styrene, $M_w = \text{ca. } 140\,000 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$) and small amounts (0.5–1.5 wt%) of **2** were prepared by combining THF solutions of the two components and solvent-casting the mixtures into molds. Evaporation of the solvent overnight was followed by drying of the films in vacuum for 24 h at room temperature to afford films with a thickness of ca. 100 μm . Under illumination with UV light ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 365 \text{ nm}$), films of all compositions show the characteristic orange excimer emission and the fluorescence spectra are accordingly dominated by a band centered around 632 nm (**Figure 2a,b**). In addition, a low-intensity band at 502 nm can be observed in the spectra, indicating the presence of a residual fraction of non-aggregated cyano-OPVs. The relative intensity of this monomer band decreases with increasing concentration of **2**, and appears to level off at a concentration of 1 wt% (**Figure 2b**). As observed for the neat **2** (*vide supra*), melting of solvent-cast SBS/**2** blends by heating to 190 °C shifts the fluorescence to the monomer-based emission (**Figure S7a**). Interestingly, considerable monomer emission remained when the sample was allowed to cool back to room temperature (**Figure S7b**). Thermogravimetric analyses (TGA) reveal that weight loss of compounds **1** and **2** only sets in above 400 °C (**Figure S8**), suggesting that this effect is not due to chemical degradation. Instead, a substantial fraction of the dye moieties does not re-

aggregate upon cooling, likely because they are trapped in the glassy poly(styrene) phase of the SBS. The residual green emission in melt-processed blends could, however, be significantly reduced by increasing the concentration of **2** to ≥ 2 wt%, as plots of the ratio of monomer to excimer emission intensities (I_M/I_E) against concentration show (**Figure S9**).

The stress-strain curves of specimen of solvent-cast SBS/**2** blends show a steep initial slope and a yield point around 10% strain when subjected to uniaxial tensile deformation for the first time (**Figure S10a,b**); such plastic deformation behavior was previously reported for SBS with interconnected glassy poly(styrene) (PS) domains.^[39,40] Subsequent stress-strain curves (*i.e.*, after destruction of connections between PS domains) show the typical behavior of a (physically) cross-linked elastomer with an elongation at break beyond 500% (**Figure S10a,b**). To investigate the mechanofluorochromic response in tension, fluorescence spectra of the solvent-cast SBS blends with 0.5 wt% of **2** were recorded *in-situ*. The monomer emission intensity at 502 nm increased when the pristine sample was deformed for the first time to a strain of 730% (**Figure 2c**). Even though plastic deformation occurs in the first stretch, the spectra recorded after relaxation match those of the pristine sample (spectra acquired with 40 min delay). Monomer emission was observed to substantially increase when samples were stretched again (*i.e.*, after the first deformation/relaxation cycle) to 730% strain, while the emission spectra after relaxation are again similar to those of the pristine sample (**Figure 2c**). The spectral changes can be expressed by the ratio of monomer-to-excimer emission intensities (I_M/I_E) recorded at 502 and 632 nm, respectively. Thus, the I_M/I_E ratio measured over several cycles of stretching an originally pristine sample to 730% strain and subsequent relaxation to 0% strain clearly reflects that the fluorescence color change is less pronounced in the first than in subsequent cycles (**Figure 2d**). One might also deduce that the sample “fatigues” a bit between the first and the fifth cycle, as I_M/I_E appears to slightly drop in the stretched and increase in the relaxed state. The data unambiguously show that macroscopic mechanical stress is transferred to the cyano-OPV aggregates, disrupting the

latter into monomeric species. The observed increase of the response after a first deformation/relaxation cycle suggests that the separation of a fraction of aggregates is hampered by the connected glassy PS domains in solvent-cast samples; all subsequent experiments were hence carried out with samples deformed beyond the yield point to 730% strain. Notably, the reversible mechanochromic response of SBS/2 blends reflect the elastic deformation behavior of the matrix, whereas solvent-cast SBS blends with 0.1–1 wt% of untethered cyano-OPV 1 exhibit comparable excimer formation without showing a chromic response upon tensile deformation (**Figure S11**). Together, these findings corroborate that the deformation of a rubbery matrix is not sufficient to disrupt excimer aggregates and that stress-transfer must occur via chain entanglement of the aggregachromic macromolecule 2 in the poly(butadiene) domains.

To determine the influence of the weight fraction of 2 in SBS blends, solvent-cast samples with 0.5–1.5 wt% of 2 were prepared and the emission intensity ratio (I_M/I_E) was determined from spectra recorded before and after uniaxial tensile deformation to 730% strain (**Figure 3a**). The comparison of the I_M/I_E ratio indicates that SBS/2 blends with weight fractions of 0.5–1 wt% of 2 display the largest fluorescence change. The response of these elastomeric samples to mechanical stimuli was accordingly reflected by a reversible shift of the emission color from orange to green that is clearly discernible to the unassisted eye when UV light ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 365 \text{ nm}$) was used for illumination (**Figure 3b**), whereas blends with >1 wt% of 2 show a less pronounced contrast, on account of the increased excimer contribution in the stretched state (**Figure S12**). Additional investigations were conducted to determine the deformation-time-response relationship in the solvent-cast SBS blend with 0.5 wt% of 2. As a first experiment, the fluorescence response as a function of applied strain was explored. Thus, a plot of the I_M/I_E ratio determined from spectra measured at strains between 200–730% shows that the signal continuously increases and can, hence, serve as a measure of deformation (**Figure 3c**). The normalized trace mirrors the stress-strain curve (**Figure S10b**),

reflecting that the fraction of monomeric cyano-OPVs increases with the extent of deformation up to a maximum just before the samples fails. Upon failure, the stress is released and the samples' original color and I_M/I_E are restored (**Figure S13**). Moreover, a sample was stretched to 730% strain and the deformation was maintained while the I_M/I_E emission intensity ratio was monitored over time (**Figure 3d**). In this case, a slight initial increase of the I_M/I_E ratio in the first 5 min after reaching 730% strain was observed, but then I_M/I_E decreased over the course of 2 h until the original I_M/I_E was restored. These findings suggest that **2** is sufficiently mobile to re-aggregate over time in the deformed elastic SBS matrix.

In addition to the solvent-cast samples, we also investigated the mechanochromic response of a melt-processed blend of SBS with **2**; based on screening experiments (*vide supra*), a concentration of 2 wt% of **2** was chosen. The stress-strain curves of this material show a less pronounced yield point at a lower stress when deformed for the first time, as melt-processing imparts a lower extent of interconnected PS domains,^[39,40] while ensuing stress-strain curves mirror those of solvent-cast samples (**Figure S10c,d**). Gratifyingly, a change of the fluorescence color from orange to green is clearly discernible by the unassisted eye upon uniaxial tensile deformation of such SBS/**2** (2 wt%) samples to 730% strain, and the excimer-centered emission color is recovered upon relaxation (**Figure S14a**). The emission intensity ratio (I_M/I_E) determined at strains of 0 and 730% reflects the reversible mechanochromic response for multiple cycles of deformation and relaxation (**Figure S14b**). Moreover, the I_M/I_E ratio measured at strains between 200–700% shows that the fraction of monomeric cyano-OPV moieties continuously increases as a function of applied strain (**Figure S14c**), mirroring the stress-strain curve. Thus, while a larger amount of the telechelic cyano-OPV **2** is required to form sufficient aggregates in melt-processed SBS blends, the mechanochromic response resembles the reversible and ratiometric behavior of solvent-cast blends.

Beyond the use of **2** in blends with SBS, poly(ϵ -caprolactone) as well as trans-1,4-poly(isoprene) were also investigated as matrices. Thus, blends of **2** with PCL ($M_n = 80\,000\text{ g mol}^{-1}$) as well as PI ($M_w = 400\,000\text{ g mol}^{-1}$) were prepared by casting mixtures from THF and drying. The blends were compression molded (100 °C, 1 ton) into films with a thickness of ca. 200 μm (see Supporting Information for details). Blends of PI with 0.5 wt% of **2** display the characteristic orange emission color associated with excimer aggregates. However, the fluorescence spectrum reveals that, in addition to the excimer band at 632 nm, considerable monomer emission at 502 nm occurs (**Figure 4a**). Likely on account of the increased polarity of PCL (vis à vis PI, SBS, and **2**), films of this matrix blended with only 0.1 wt% of **2** exhibit the characteristic orange excimer fluorescence, while spectra again show that substantial monomer emission is at play (**Figure 4b**). Uniaxial tensile deformation of dog-bone-shaped specimen of PCL or PI blended with **2** mirror the stress-strain curves of the respective neat, semi-crystalline polymers (**Figure S15**). In both cases, plastic deformation leads to a visually discernible orange-to-green shift of the fluorescence color ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 365\text{ nm}$), and an increased monomer emission intensity is apparent from spectra recorded before and immediately after deformation (**Figure 4**). The monomer-to-excimer emission intensity ratio (I_M/I_E) reflects these changes (**Figure S16**). Monitoring samples of PI/**2** (0.5 wt%) immediately after failure reveals no significant changes over time (**Figure S16a**). By contrast, the I_M/I_E ratio of PCL/**2** (0.1 wt%) blends after failure continuously increases over the course of 8 h, after which the value remains constant (**Figure S16b**). While the origin of this particular effect is not yet clear, our findings corroborate that different types of polymers can be readily rendered mechanochromic by blending with the aggregachromic macromolecule **2**. In the investigated blends, the response is found to vary, presumably as a function of the mobility of **2** within the respective matrices. Thus, sample deformation is followed by recovery of excimer emission over time for SBS blends, continued disruption of excimer aggregates in PCL blends, while no further changes are observed for PI blends.

3. Conclusions

Mechanofluorochromic polymers have been prepared by simple dispersion of aggregachromic dyes, but this approach has been mostly limited to semi-crystalline matrices. Employing an aggregachromic macromolecule that consist of a poly(ethylene-*co*-butylene) telechelic functionalized at the termini with excimer-forming cyano-OPV chromophores extends the scope of this approach. Thus, blending the latter renders poly(styrene-*b*-butadiene-*b*-styrene), poly(ϵ -caprolactone), and poly(isoprene) responsive to mechanical stimulation. Our findings show that the stress-transfer from the matrix to the dye aggregates is significantly improved, presumably due to entanglements between the matrix and the aggregachromic macromolecule. In this way, elastic deformation is reversibly translated into a fluorescence color change and the viscoelastic response upon deformation can be potentially monitored spectroscopically. Moreover, the monomer-to-excimer emission intensity ratio can be used to correlate spectral changes to the extent of deformation. The herein reported approach, hence, significantly expands the utility of aggregachromic dyes as a simple means to prepare blend-based mechanochromic materials with the potential for facile and wide-spread application.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information including Figures S1–S17, **Movie M1** and a comprehensive account of all experimental details, including synthetic procedures, analytical data, and NMR spectra of all compounds is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Figure 1. **a)** Chemical structures of the asymmetric cyano-OPV derivative **1** and the cyano-OPV-functionalized telechelic poly(ethylene-*co*-butylene) **2** (with $M_n = 4500 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$; $m \approx 0.36$, $n \approx 0.64$, $p \approx 44$). **b)** Photographs and fluorescence spectra ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 375 \text{ nm}$) of a solvent-cast film of **2** before and after heating above the melting transition (126°C). **c)** Photographs and fluorescence spectra ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 375 \text{ nm}$) of a solvent-cast film of **2** before and after mechanical stimulation by grinding. **d)** Photographs showing the reversible fluorescence color change upon shearing a PEB/**2** mixture (90:10 w/w) for ca. 10 sec. All images were taken under illumination with 365 nm UV light and the spectra were normalized so that the intensity of monomer emission at 525 nm and excimer emission at 636 nm match.

Figure 2. **a)** Photographs of pristine, solvent-cast films of poly(styrene-*b*-butadiene-*b*-styrene) blends containing 0.5–1.5 wt% of **2** (as indicated). **b)** Comparison of the fluorescence spectra of SBS blends with 0.5–1.5 wt% of **2**. **c)** Comparison of the fluorescence spectra of a pristine film of the SBS/2 blend (0.5 wt%), the emission upon first deformation to 730% strain, after relaxation, second deformation to 730% strain, and after repeated deformation and relaxation. **d)** Plot of the ratio of monomer-to-excimer emission intensities (I_M/I_E) determined at 502 and 632 nm for a pristine solvent-cast film of SBS/2 (0.5 wt%) and during multiple cycles of deformation to 730% strain and relaxation to 0% strain. All images were taken under illumination with 365 nm UV light. For spectroscopy, samples were excited with $\lambda_{ex} = 375$ nm and measurements of relaxed samples were carried out 40 min after the force was removed. Spectra in **c)** and **d)** are normalized for the maximum emission intensity of the excimer at 636 nm.

Figure 4. Fluorescence spectra of thin films of **a)** trans-1,4-polyisoprene/2 (0.5 wt%) and **b)** poly(ϵ -caprolactone)/2 (0.1 wt%) measured before (orange line) and after (green line) tensile deformation until sample failure. The photographs show samples after deformation and were taken under illumination with 365 nm UV light. All spectra were acquired with $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 375$ nm and are normalized for the maximum emission intensity of the excimer at 632 nm for **a)** and at 630 nm for **b)**.

The use of a telechelic aggregachromic macromolecule allows to bestow mechanochromic responsive behavior onto different types of polymer matrices. The stress-transfer from the matrix to the dye aggregates is found to be significantly improved so that an elastic deformation is reversibly translated into a fluorescence color change, significantly expanding the utility of blend-based mechanochromic materials.

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Mechanoresponsive Luminescent Polymer Blends Based on an Excimer-Forming Telechelic Macromolecule

reversible mechanochromism

Supporting Information

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Mechanoresponsive Luminescent Polymer Blends Based on an Excimer-Forming Telechelic Macromolecule

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1. Supporting Data

Figure S1. Schematic of the synthesis of hydroxyl functionalized cyano-oligo(*p*-phenylene vinylene) derivative **1** that was carried out by adapting a previously reported procedure.^[1] *Reagents and conditions:* (a) K_2CO_3 , acetone, 68 °C, overnight, 80%; (b), K_2CO_3 , acetone, 68 °C, overnight, 53%; (c) K_2CO_3 , DMF, 75 °C, 8 h, 61%; (d) potassium *tert*-butoxide (1 M), tetrabutylammonium hydroxide (1 M), 2-methyl-2-butanol / THF (3:1), 50 °C, 1 h, 86%.

Figure S2. a) UV-Vis absorption spectrum of **1** in chloroform ($c = 0.033 \text{ mmol L}^{-1}$). b) Fluorescence spectra ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 375 \text{ nm}$) of **1** in chloroform solution (green line, $c = 1.4 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$) and of the corresponding microcrystalline solid **1** obtained after drying the chloroform solution (orange line). The spectra were normalized so that the maximum emission intensities of the monomer (505 nm) and the excimer (617 nm) emission match. The insets show photographs of the chloroform solution and of the microcrystalline solid under illumination with 365 nm UV light.

Figure S3. Schematic of the synthesis of the bis-acyl chloride terminated telechelic poly(ethylene-*co*-butylene) **6** and its condensation with the cyano-OPV derivative **1** to yield excimer-forming telechelic macromolecule **2** over two steps. The telechelic bis(3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)propanoic acid)-functionalized poly(ethylene-*co*-butylene) was prepared from commercial bis-hydroxyl terminated poly(ethylene-*co*-butylene) ($M_n = 3100 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$; Krasol HLBH-P 3000) as described elsewhere.^{[2],[3]} *Reagents and conditions:* (i) SOCl_2 , CHCl_3 , r.t., overnight, quantitative; (ii) CHCl_3 , r.t., 48 h, 42%.

Figure S4. a) UV-vis absorption spectrum of **2** in chloroform ($c = 0.017 \text{ mmol L}^{-1}$). b) Fluorescence spectra ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 375 \text{ nm}$) of **2** in chloroform solution (green line, $c = 1.4 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$) and of the corresponding microcrystalline solid **2** obtained after drying the chloroform solution (orange line). The spectra were normalized so that the maximum emission intensities of the monomer (505 nm) and excimer (634 nm) emission match. The insets show photographs of the chloroform solution and the microcrystalline solid illuminated with 365 nm UV light.

Figure S5. Differential scanning calorimetry traces showing the first and second heating and cooling scans of a film of **2** solvent-cast from chloroform. Data were acquired with a heating and cooling rate of $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ in a nitrogen atmosphere.

Figure S6. a) Photographs illustrating the thermochromism of the cyano-OPV-terminated telechelic **2**. In clock-wise sequence from top-left: (i) film obtained by solvent-casting of a chloroform solution, (ii) upon heating to a temperature of 116 °C, (iii) upon heating above the melting transition to 126 °C, and (iv) after cooling back to room temperature (r.t.). All images were taken under illumination with 365 nm UV light. b) Fluorescence spectra of **2** recorded on the samples depicted in panel a) at room temperature, 116 °C, 126 °C, and after cooling back to room temperature ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 375$ nm).

Figure S7. a) Fluorescence spectra ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 375 \text{ nm}$) of films of a pristine blend of SBS and **2** (1 wt%) obtained by solvent-casting from THF (orange line), while heated to 126°C (dark green line), and while heated to 190°C (light green line). b) Fluorescence spectra ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 375 \text{ nm}$) of films of the pristine blend of SBS and **2** (1 wt%) cast from THF (orange line) and a sample first melted at 190°C for 10 min and cooled down to room temperature (green line). The spectra were normalized so that the maximum emission intensities of the excimer (632 nm) match. The insets show photographs of the solvent-cast (right) and melted (left) samples illuminated by 365 nm UV light.

Figure S8. Thermogravimetric analyses of compounds **1** and **2** recorded under ambient conditions at a heating rate of $10^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$.

Figure S9. Plot of the ratio of monomer-to-excimer emission intensities (I_M / I_E) determined at 502 and 632 nm for melt-processed SBS blends with 1, 1.5, 2, 2.5, 3, 4, or 5 wt% of **2**. For each concentration, three samples were prepared and measured.

Figure S10. Stress-strain curves for three consecutive deformations to a strain of 500% of dog-bone-shaped samples of (a) solvent-cast SBS, b) a solvent-cast SBS/2 blend (0.5 wt%), c) melt-processed SBS, and (d) a melt-processed SBS/2 blend (2 wt%). Sample dimensions were: $40 \times 5 \times 0.2$ mm in all cases. The stress-strain measurements shown are representative of three replicates.

Figure S11. a) Photographs of pristine solvent-cast blends of SBS with 0.1, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, and 1 wt% of the parent cyano-OPV **1**. b) Photographs of the same samples as shown in panel (a) upon tensile deformation to 730% strain. All images were taken under illumination with 365 nm UV light. c) Plot of the I_M/I_E ratio calculated using emission intensities recorded at 502 and 632 nm for solvent-cast SBS blends with 0.1, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, and 1 wt% of **1** before (orange symbol) and while stretching (green symbol) to a strain of 730% (evaluation of three samples). All measurements on stretched samples were carried out after first conditioning the samples, which involved deformation to a strain of 730% followed by relaxation and waiting for 40 min.

Figure S12. Comparison of the fluorescence spectra ($\lambda_{ex} = 375$ nm) of SBS blends with 0.5–1.5 wt% of **2** while stretched to a strain of 730%. The spectra are normalized so that the maximum emission intensities of the excimer (632 nm) match. All measurements were carried out after first conditioning the samples, which involved deformation to a strain of 730% followed by relaxation and waiting for 40 min.

Figure S13. Comparison of the fluorescence spectra ($\lambda_{ex} = 375$ nm) of SBS blends with 0.5 wt% of **2**, pristine (orange line), while stretched to a strain of 730 % (green line), directly after failure (dark grey), and 40 min after failure (light grey). The spectra are normalized so that the maximum emission intensities of the excimer (632 nm) match. The measurement of the stretched sample was carried out after first conditioning the sample, which involved deformation to a strain of 730 % followed by relaxation and waiting for 40 min.

Figure S14. a) Photographs of pristine melt-processed SBS blends with 2 wt% of **2** before and during tensile deformation to a strain of 730 %. The images were taken under illumination with 365 nm UV light. b) Plot of the I_M/I_E ratio recorded at 502 and 632 nm for a pristine melt-processed sample of SBS/**2** (2 wt%) and during multiple cycles of deformation to 730 % strain and relaxation to 0 % strain. c) Plot of the ratio of monomer-to-excimer emission intensities (I_M/I_E) recorded at 502 and 632 nm for a melt-processed sample of SBS/**2** (2 wt%) as a function of the applied strain. Spectra were recorded under excitation with $\lambda_{ex} = 375$ nm and measurements of relaxed samples were carried out 40 min after the force had been removed.

Figure S15. a) Comparison of the stress-strain curves of dog-bone-shaped samples ($40 \times 5 \times 0.2$ mm) of neat poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (black line) and poly(ϵ -caprolactone) blended with 0.1 wt% of **2** (blue line). b) Comparison of the stress-strain curves of dog-bone-shaped samples ($40 \times 5 \times 0.2$ mm) of neat *trans*-1,4-poly(isoprene) (black line) and *trans*-1,4-poly(isoprene) blended with 0.5 wt% of **5** (blue line). The stress-strain measurements shown are representative of three replicates.

Figure S16. a) Plot of the I_M/I_E ratio recorded at 502 and 632 nm for a melt-processed blend of PI/2 (0.5 wt%) before and immediately after tensile deformation until sample failure, as well as over the course of 15 h after failure. b) Plot of the ratio of monomer-to-excimer emission intensities (I_M/ I_E) recorded at 508 and 630 nm for a melt-processed blend of PCL/2 (0.1 wt%) before and immediately after tensile deformation until sample failure, as well as over the course of 24 h after failure.

Figure S17. a) Photographs of the hydroxyl-substituted cyano-OPV **1** (top) and of solvent-cast films of **2** (bottom) before (left) and after (right) mechanical deformation by grinding. All images were taken under illumination with 365 nm UV light. b) Fluorescence spectra of **1** and **2** recorded after extensive grinding ($\lambda_{ex} = 375$ nm). The spectra were normalized so that the maximum emission intensities of the excimer (637 nm) match.

2. Supporting Experimental Section

2.1. Materials and Instrumentation

2,5-Dimethoxybenzene-1,4-dicarboxaldehyde, 1,6-dibromohexane, anhydrous potassium carbonate, 2-methyl-2-butanol, *p*-toluenesulfonyl chloride, anhydrous pyridine, tetrabutylammonium iodide, thionyl chloride, triethylamine, methyl 3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)propionate, 12-bromo-1-dodecanol, *p*-hexylphenol, anhydrous sodium sulfate, hydrochloric acid, ammonium chloride, magnesium sulfate, sodium hydroxide, poly(styrene-*b*-butadiene-*b*-styrene) (SBS, styrene 30 wt%, M_w = ca. 140 000), *trans*-1,4-polyisoprene (M_w = 400 000 g mol⁻¹), and poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (M_n = ca. 80 000) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Potassium *tert*-butoxide (1 M solution in *tert*-butanol), tetrabutylammonium hydroxide (1 M solution in methanol), and extra dry tetrahydrofuran (THF) were purchased from Acros Organics. 4-Hydroxybenzylcyanide and *p*-hexylphenol were purchased from TCI. Acetone, dichloromethane, dimethylformamide, methanol, hexane, and toluene were purchased from VWR. Bis-hydroxyl terminated poly(ethylene-*co*-butylene) (M_n = 3100 g mol⁻¹; degree of functionalization ca. 1.9; trade name Krasol HLBH-P 3000) was kindly donated by Cray Valley Company. The bis-4-hydroxyphenyl propionate terminated poly(ethylene-*co*-butylene) was prepared from bis-hydroxyl terminated poly(ethylene-*co*-butylene) (M_n = 3100 g mol⁻¹; degree of functionalization ca. 1.9; trade name Krasol HLBH-P 3000) following a previously reported procedure.^{[2],[3]} All reagents and solvents were purchased as analytical grade and used without further purification. All spectroscopic investigations were carried out with spectroscopy grade solvents. Deuterated solvents were purchased from Cambridge Isotope Laboratories, Inc.

Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy was carried out at 297.2 K on a Bruker Avance DPX 400 spectrometer at frequencies of 400.19 MHz for ¹H nuclei and 100.63 MHz for ¹³C nuclei. Spectra were calibrated to the residual solvent peak of CDCl₃ (7.26 ppm ¹H NMR; 77.16 ppm ¹³C NMR). Data were evaluated with the MestReNova software suite (v 12.0) and all chemical shifts δ are reported in parts per million (ppm) with coupling constant in Hz (multiplicity: s = singlet, d = doublet, dd = double doublet, t = triplet, m = multiplet, br = broad signal).

Mass spectrometry (MS) was carried out as a service measurement either at the mass spectrometry service of the Institute of Chemistry of the University of Fribourg or at the molecular and biomolecular analysis service MoBiAS of ETH Zürich. At the University of Fribourg, a Bruker FTMS 4.7T BioAPEX II equipped with a ComiSource 1.0 and operated in

positive ionization mode was used for high-resolution electrospray ionization mass spectrometry (ESI-MS) and matrix-assisted laser desorption ionization (MALDI) mass spectrometry was carried out on a Bruker ultrafleXtreme using *trans*-2[3-(4-*tert*-butylphenyl)-2-methyl-2-propenylidene]malononitrile (DCTB) as the matrix materials. At ETH Zürich, high-resolution electrospray ionization mass spectrometry (ESI-MS) was measured on a Bruker maXis Q-TOF instrument operated in positive ionization mode and high-resolution matrix-assisted laser desorption ionization (MALDI) mass spectrometry was carried out on a Bruker 9.4T FT-ICR solariX using DCTB as the matrix. Spectra from both instruments were calibrated internally using Agilent ESI L low concentration tuning mix (AGG1969-85000).

UV-Vis spectroscopy was carried out with a JASCO V670 spectrometer and data were treated with the Spectra Manager software suite. Quartz cuvettes (1 cm) from Hellma were used to measure the absorption from 350–800 nm.

Solution phase fluorescence spectroscopy was carried out with a Varian Cary Eclipse spectrometer and the temperature was controlled with a Varian Cary Single Cell Peltier Accessory. For all samples, data were collected in the range of 450–700 nm with an excitation wavelength of $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 430$ nm using quartz cuvettes (1 cm path length).

Solid state fluorescence spectroscopy was recorded in reflection geometry with an Ocean Optics USB4000-FL spectrometer employing an Ocean Optics LS-450 LED light source with an excitation wavelength of $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 370$ nm and an Ocean Optics Shimadzu UV-2401 PC optical fiber. Samples were placed on top of a piece of black paper as substrate and the optical fiber was oriented normal to the surface at a distance of 5 mm, resulting in a spot size of approximately 800 μm from which the diffuse reflectance was measured. Spectra were recorded before, after, or during application of mechanical stress and data were acquired with Stream basic software.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) measurements were carried out with a Mettler-Toledo STAR system operating under nitrogen atmosphere with heating/cooling rates of 3 $^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ in the range from -80 to 200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ using a sample mass of approximately 5 mg. The midpoint of the step change in the heat capacity is reported as the glass transition temperature T_{g} and the melting temperature, T_{m} , is reported based on the minimum of the major endothermic melting peaks.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was conducted in ambient condition using a Mettler-Toledo STAR thermogravimetric analyzer in the range from 25 to 600 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ with a heating rate of 10 C min^{-1} .

Tensile tests. Unless otherwise noted, stress-strain measurements were carried out with a Zwick/ Roell Z010 tensile tester equipped with a 200 N load cell. Uniaxial deformations were performed on dog-bone-shaped samples with dimensions of $40 \times 5 \times 0.1\text{--}0.3$ mm (length \times width \times thickness) that were cut from films. The strain rate was 10 mm min^{-1} and a preload of 0.1 MPa was applied. Tensile deformation with concomitant fluorescence measurements were carried out with rectangular-shaped samples with approximate dimensions of $30 \times 5 \times 0.1\text{--}0.3$ mm (length \times width \times thickness). The samples were fixed in a micro-tensile tester and uniaxial deformation to strains between 0 and 730% was applied by manually adjusting the extension, after which fluorescence measurements were immediately performed as described for solid state fluorescence spectroscopy (*vide supra*).

Photographs were taken with a Nikon D7100 digital camera equipped with an AF-S DX Zoom-NIKKOR 18-135mm lens (f/3.5-5.6G IF-ED).

2.2. Methods and Procedures

Preparation of polymer films and blends. Polymer films of a blend of SBS and compound **2** (0.25–5.0 wt%) or compound **1** (0.1–1 wt%) were prepared by addition of the appropriate amounts of the additive and the polymer (300 mg) into a glass vial container with a volume of 20 mL. The mixture was dissolved by addition of THF (15 mL) and the obtained solution was subsequently casted in a cylindrical PTFE dish with a diameter of 6 cm. The sample was left to stand at room temperature under the fume hood over night to allow the solvent to slowly evaporate. The obtained films were then placed under high vacuum for at least 24 h to completely dry the samples. Blends of **2** with poly(ϵ -caprolactone) and poly(isoprene) were prepared following the same procedure using 0.1 and 0.5 wt% of compound **2**, respectively. Reference samples of the neat polymers were processed in the same way.

Melt-processing of polymer films and blends. Polymer films of solvent-cast SBS/**2** blends were placed between PTFE sheets and melt processed at 190 °C into films with a thickness of 150 μm by employing a Carver hot press with a spacer and applying a pressure of 2 metric tons for 10 min. Upon removal of the pressure, the films were removed from the hot press and left in between the metal plates of the press to slowly cool down from 190 °C to room temperature (ca. 30 min). Blends with poly(ϵ -caprolactone) and poly(isoprene) as well as films of the neat polymers were prepared in the same way from the solvent-cast materials by processing at 100 °C and applying a pressure of 2 metric tons for 10 min.

2.3. Synthetic Procedures and Analytical Data

Synthesis of 1-(α -cyano-4-(6-(4-hexylphenoxy)hexyloxy)styryl)-4-(α -cyano-4-(12-hydroxydodecyloxy)styryl)-2,5-bismethoxybenzene 1.

2,5-Dimethoxyterephthalaldehyde (1.00 g, 2.54 mmol, 1 eq), **4** (0.8 g, 2.54 mmol, 1 eq), **5** (0.49 g, 2.54 mmol, 1 eq), dry 2-methyl-2-butanol (90 mL), and dry THF (30 mL) were added to a dried Schlenk flask under an inert nitrogen atmosphere. The mixture was heated to 50 °C and stirred for 45 min after which potassium *tert*-butoxide (0.51 mL, 1 M in methanol, 0.51 mmol, 0.2 eq) and tertbutylammonium hydroxide (10.2 mL, 1 M in methanol, 10.14 mmol, 4 eq) were simultaneously added. The mixture was stirred for 1 h at 50 °C, allowed to cool to room temperature and poured into ice-cooled methanol (1.2 L). The resulting precipitate was collected by filtration through a millipore glass vacuum filter equipped with filter membranes (Durapore, PVDF, pore size 0.45 μ m, diam. 47 mm) to yield **1** as an orange solid (1.9 g, 2.18 mmol, 86%), which was stored in the dark. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 7.88 (d, 4H, ArH, CH=C), 7.65-7.62 (d, 4H, ArH), 7.10-7.07 (d, 2H, ArH), 6.97-6.94 (d, 4H, ArH), 6.83-6.80 (d, 4H, ArH), 4.04-3.62 (m, 12H, CH₂-O, CH₃-O), 3.67-3.62 (t, 2H, CH₂-OH), 2.56-2.51 (t, 2H, ArCH₂) 1.87-1.81 (m, 6H, CH₂), 1.78-1.29 (m, 30H, CH₂), 0.90-0.86 (t, 3H, CH₃). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 160.2, 160.2, 157.2, 152.0, 135.1, 133.8, 133.8, 129.3, 127.6, 127.1, 127.0, 125.5, 118.7, 115.1, 114.4, 111.7, 110.3, 77.4, 77.3, 77.1, 76.8, 68.4, 68.2, 67.9, 63.1, 56.5, 35.2, 32.9, 31.8, 31.8, 29.7, 29.7, 29.5, 29.5, 29.4, 29.3, 29.2, 29.1, 26.1, 26.0, 26.0, 25.9, 22.7, 14.2, 13.8. HRMS (ESI): calcd. for C₅₆H₇₂N₂O₆: 891.5287 ([M+Na]⁺); found: 891.5283.

Synthesis of bis-cyano-OPV terminated telechelic poly(ethylene-*co*-butylene) 2.

(i) Bis-4-hydroxyphenyl propionate terminated poly(ethylene-*co*-butylene)^[2,3] (651 mg, 0.2 mmol) was dried in high vacuum in round bottom flask for 4 hours at 60 °C while stirring. After cooling to room temperature, dry chloroform (5 mL) and thionyl chloride (2 mL) were added, and the mixture was allowed to stir overnight at room temperature. The bis-acyl chloride terminated poly(ethylene-*co*-butylene) **6** was then obtained as a brownish viscous liquid (quantitative conversion according to ¹H NMR spectroscopy) after drying under high vacuum and used without further purification in the next step. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 7.10–7.08 (d, 4H, ArH), 6.84–6.82 (d, 4H, ArH), 3.97–3.90 (m, 4H, PEB-CH₂-O), 3.19–3.14 (t, 4H, ClCOCH₂), 2.97–2.92 (t, 4H, ArCH₂), 2–0.5 (m, CH₂, CH₃ backbone).

(ii) The bis-acyl chloride terminated poly(ethylene-*co*-butylene) **6** was dissolved in dried chloroform (10 mL). Asymmetric cyano-OPV derivative **1** (1.6 g, 2.51 mmol) was added and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 3 days. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and purified by column chromatography (Bio-BeadsTM SM-2 Resin, 100-

200 mesh; toluene) to yield **2** (380 mg, 0.08 mmol, 42 % yield) as an orange solid of polymeric appearance. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 7.88 (d, 4H, ArH, CH=C), 7.65-7.62 (d, 4H, ArH), 7.10-7.07 (t, 4H, ArH), 6.97-6.95 (d, 4H, ArH), 6.83-6.80 (d, 4H, ArH), 4.07-3.92 (m, 18H, CH₂-O, CH₃-O, CH₂), 2.90-2.86 (t, 2H, CH₂), 2.60-2.52 (m, 4H, CH₂), 1.82-0.83 (m, CH₂, CH₃ backbone). MS (MALDI): calcd. for C₃₀₆H₅₁₀N₄O₁₆ (m+n=44 [M+Na]⁺): 4524.3; found: 4523.8.

Synthesis of 2-(4-(6-bromohexyloxy)phenyl)acetonitrile **3**.

1,6-Dibromohexane (5.7 mL, 37.5 mmol, 5 eq) and 2-(4-hydroxyphenyl)acetonitrile (1 g, 7.5 mmol, 1 eq) were added to a dried Schlenk flask under an inert nitrogen atmosphere and dissolved in dry acetone (250 mL). Potassium carbonate (2.07 g, 15 mmol, 2 eq) was added and the mixture was heated to reflux (68 °C) for 12 h. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature, dichloromethane (100 mL) was added, the mixture was washed two times with 1 M HCl (100 mL), once with saturated aqueous NaCl solution (100 mL), and once with deionized water (100 mL). The organic phase was dried over Na₂SO₄, filtered, and the solvents were removed under reduced pressure. The residue was taken up in dichloromethane (4 mL) and precipitation in cold hexane (20 mL) furnished **3** as a colorless solid (1.79 g, 6.06 mmol, 80%). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 7.23 (d, 2H, ArH), 6.90-6.87 (dt, 2H, ArH), 3.98-3.94 (m, 2H, OCH₂), 3.68 (s, 2H, NC-CH₂), 3.44-3.41 (t, 2H, CH₂), 1.93-1.86 (quint, 2H, CH₂), 1.83-1.77 (q, 2H, CH₂), 1.56-1.50 (m, 4H, CH₂). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 158.97 (1C, C-Ar), 129.20 (2C, C-Ar), 121.78 (1C, C-Ar), 118.34 (1C, C-CN), 115.23 (2C, C-Ar), 68.00 (1C, CH₂-O), 33.90, 32.80, 29.17, 28.04, 25.42, 22.98 (6C, CH₂). HRMS (ESI): calcd. for C₁₄H₁₈BrNO: 318.0469 ([M+Na]⁺); found: 318.0464.

Synthesis of 2-(4-(6-(4-hexylphenoxy)hexyloxy)phenyl)acetonitrile **4**.

2-(4-(6-Bromohexyloxy)phenyl)acetonitrile **3** (1.42 g, 4.9 mmol, 1 eq) and 4-hexylphenol (1.07 g, 6.0 mmol, 1.2 eq) were added to a dried Schlenk flask under an inert nitrogen atmosphere and dissolved in dry acetone (150 mL). Potassium carbonate (1.38 g, 9.9 mmol, 2 eq) was added and the mixture was heated to reflux (68 °C) for 72 h. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature, dichloromethane (80 mL) was added, the mixture was washed two times with 1 M HCl (120 mL), once with saturated aqueous NaCl solution (100 mL), and once with deionized water (100 mL). The organic phase was dried over Na₂SO₄, filtered, and the solvents were removed under reduced pressure. The residue was recrystallized in dichloromethane and hexane to furnish **4** as an off-white solid (1.29 g, 3.28 mmol, 67 %). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 7.23-7.21 (d, 2H, ArH), 7.09-7.07 (d, 2H, ArH), 6.91-6.87 (dt, 2H, ArH), 6.83-6.79 (dt, 2H, ArH), 3.98-3.93 (q, 4H, CH₂-O), 3.68

(s, 2H, NC-CH₂), 2.56-2.52 (t, 2H, CH₂), 1.82-1.80 (m, 4C, CH₂), 1.58-1.52 (m, 6C, CH₂), 1.36-1.28(m, 6C, CH₂), 0.90-0.87 (t, 3C, CH₃). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 159.0 (1C, C-Ar), 157.2 (1C, C-Ar), 135.1 (1C, C-Ar), 129.3 (2C, C-Ar), 129.2 (2C, C-Ar), 121.7 (1C, C-Ar), 118.4 (1C, C-CN), 115.2 (2C, C-Ar), 114.4 (2C, C-Ar), 68.1 (1C, CH₂-O), 67.9 (1C, CH₂-O), 35.2, 31.9, 31.9, 29.4, 29.3, 29.1, 26.1, 26.0, 23.0, 22.8 (10C, CH₂), 14.2 (1C, CH₃). HRMS (ESI): calcd. for C₂₆H₃₅NO₂: 416.2565 ([M+Na]⁺); found: 416.2560.

Synthesis of 2-(4-(12-hydroxydodecyloxy)phenyl)acetonitrile **5**.

Potassium carbonate (16.58 g, 120 mmol, 2 eq) and 2-(4-hydroxyphenyl)acetonitrile (5.33 g, 40 mmol, 1 eq) were added to a dried Schlenk flask under an inert nitrogen atmosphere, dry DMF (90 mL) was added, and the mixture was heated to 75 °C. To this mixture, a solution of 12-bromododecan-1-ol (11.09 g, 42 mmol, 1.2 eq) in dry DMF (40 mL) was added and the resulting mixture was stirred for 8 h at 75 °C. The reaction was quenched by addition of an ice-cooled saturated aqueous NH₄Cl solution (50 mL) and the resulting colorless precipitate was collected. The residue was taken up in dichloromethane (5 mL) and precipitation in cold hexane (150 mL) furnished **5** as an orange solid (7.8 g, 24.6 mmol, 61 %). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 7.22-7.20 (dt, 2H, ArH), 6.89-6.87 (dt, 2H, ArH), 3.96-3.93 (t, 2H, CH₂-O), 3.67 (s, 2H, CH₂-CN), 3.65-3.62 (t, 2H, CH₂-OH), 1.81-1.74 (quint, 2H, CH₂), 1.60-1.53 (quint, 2H, CH₂), 1.48-1.43 (quint, 2H, CH₂), 1.41-1.28 (m 15H, CH₂). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 159.1 (1C, C-Ar), 129.2 (2C, C-Ar), 121.7 (1C, C-Ar), 118.4 (1C, C-CN), 115.2 (2C, C-Ar), 68.3 (1C, CH₂-O), 63.2 (1C, CH₂-OH), 33.0, 29.7, 29.7, 29.6, 29.5, 29.3, 26.1, 25.9, 23.0 (11C, CH₂). HRMS (ESI): calcd. for C₂₀H₃₁NO₂: 340.2252 ([M+Na]⁺); found: 340.2247.

3. Supporting Molecular Characterization

^1H NMR spectrum (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) of **1**.

^{13}C NMR spectrum (CDCl_3 , 101 MHz) of **1**.

^1H NMR spectrum (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) of **2**.

MALDI spectrum of **2**.

^1H NMR spectrum (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) of **3**.

^{13}C NMR spectrum (CDCl_3 , 101 MHz) of **3**

^1H NMR spectrum (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) of **4**.

^{13}C NMR spectrum (CDCl_3 , 101 MHz) of **4**

^1H NMR spectrum (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) of **5**.

^{13}C NMR spectrum (CDCl_3 , 101 MHz) of **5**.

^1H NMR spectrum (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) of **6**.

4. References

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